

THE KASHMIR-ISRAEL-PALESTINE ANALOGY: PROPAGANDA NARRATIVES AND PAKISTAN'S DIPLOMATIC RESPONSE

Dr. Armaghan Farid^{*1}, Dr. Ghulam Sarwar²

^{*1}Visiting Faculty Member Department of Political Science University of the Punjab Lahore

²SSE, School Education Department, Government of the Punjab, Pakistan.

¹armaghannfaridd@gmail.com, ²sarwar69@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15727738>

Keywords

Kashmir, Palestine, Israel, Diplomatic position, Constructivism

Article History

Received on 17 May 2025

Accepted on 17 June 2025

Published on 24 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Armaghan Farid

Abstract

Pakistan's alignment with Kashmir and Palestine conflicts is a reflection of its ascribed role and constructs its identity as a Muslim-majority state advocating oppressed Muslim populations and how this shapes its foreign policy. The conflicts serve as platforms for Pakistan to assert its ideological alignment a diplomatic positioning within the Islamic world. This qualitative research study discusses how propaganda influences public opinion and constructs identities that shape diplomatic responses. The theoretical framework discusses constructivist framing, and neocolonial theory to understand Pakistan's stance about Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflicts. Interpretivism and religious ethical framework explore the role of Pakistan's foreign policy towards Israel. This research study contends that Pakistan has to shift from conventional to modern political spectrum and constructs new policy towards Israel to start foreign relations and to counter India in the South Asian region. Pakistan's diplomatic ties with Israel has the potential to uplift Pakistan's moral standing and global influence.

INTRODUCTION

The Kashmir and Palestine unresolved conflicts remain emblematic of global struggles over self-determination, occupation, and international justice often framed as Muslim humanitarian crisis and remained focal points in Pakistan's foreign policy. The Kashmir and Palestine conflicts are more than foreign policy issues for Pakistan because they are integral to its national identity, ideological orientation, and strategic calculus. These conflicts serve as platforms for Pakistan to assert its ideological alignment and diplomatic positioning within the Islamic world. However, over the decades, Pakistan has maintained a consistent diplomatic posture advocating for the rights of Kashmiris and Palestinians. Therefore, this article investigates the theoretical and philosophical underpinnings of Pakistan's diplomatic response, analyzes its practical. These conflicts have been central

to South Asian and Middle Eastern geopolitics for over seven decades framed as parallel struggles for Muslim population under occupation. International political landscape is shaped not only by hard power and diplomacy but also by the strategic use of narratives and propaganda. States leverage propaganda as a tool to construct legitimacy, garner international support, and influence public opinion in the context of unresolved conflict of Kashmir-Israel-Palestine. The aim of this research study is to analyze Pakistan's diplomatic, strategic, narratives, alignments concerning Kashmir-Israel-Palestine analogy. Although, this study contends that Pakistan constructs its diplomatic approach to Kashmir-Israel-Palestine not merely as a foreign policy concern but as a normative, ideological, and identity-based pursuit shaped by geopolitical realities. This critical analysis argues that

with changing dynamics and narratives of international politics, Pakistan needs to redefine foreign policy to mitigate the influence of Indian-Israel bonhomie for the security of the South Asia. The objectives of this research are to explore how Pakistan constructs and disseminates narratives around Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflicts in international forums. This is an attempt to investigate the role of public diplomacy and symbolic politics in reinforcing Pakistan's positions on Kashmir and Palestine. Pakistan's historical rival India as a regional competitor attempts to influence the South Asian region by controlling economy, geopolitics, and geographical landscape. Therefore, Israel and the USA support India to gain the status of South Asian giant to counter China economically and politically. Israel and the USA both equally have multifaceted interests in the South Asia to maintain their influence and prolonged colonial hegemony. On the contrast, Pakistan's religious, ideological, and sentimental affiliations with the Muslim people of Kashmir-Palestine construct the foreign and diplomatic narratives for Pakistan. Therefore, this study has a twofold aim: to dissect the propaganda mechanisms Pakistan employs to frame the Kashmir-Palestine conflicts and to explore how these narratives inform and reinforce its diplomatic behavior. These two reveal the consistencies and contradictions in rhetorical and strategic responses of Pakistan. However, these narratives are often constrained by geopolitical realities and competing national interests in relation to evolving regional alignments. The Indo-Pak rivalry due to Kashmir, Israel-USA-India bonhomie, and Israel backed Indian worrisome actions are concerning for the regional peace. However, Pakistan draws parallels between these two conflicts by framing them through the lens of violation and occupation and its diplomatic rhetoric remains central to territorial integrity. The Palestinian conflict provides a platform for Pakistan to consolidate its identity as a leader of Muslim Ummah. The research questions of this study are:

- To what extent does Pakistan frame Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflicts in its official diplomatic response?
- How does Pakistan construct and disseminate propaganda narratives on Kashmir and Palestine?

Research Methods

This qualitative research study Kashmir-Israel-Palestine Conflict uses the methodology of critical analysis. The nature of research design is content analysis and discusses theoretical and philosophical framework to understand the propaganda narratives and Pakistan's diplomatic response for policy orientation. This study relies on secondary data sources.

Literature Review

The analogy of conflicts of Kashmir-Israel-Palestine and Pakistan's diplomatic response requires an investigation of existing literature to understand the propaganda narratives that influences the decision-making in foreign policy.

The disputed territory of Kashmir has remained the core issue of Indo-Pak rivalry since 1947. India revoked Article 370 in 2019, since; relations between them have been dismal. Both countries have a long history of mistrust, broken promises, and violations of treaties (Ullah et al, 2022, Shamim et al, 2024). The conflict among two nuclear nations intensified security dilemma making Kashmir not just a bilateral issue but a potential global flashpoint. Indo-Pak partition of 1947 recorded as one of the deadliest migration in the world history (Hussain et al., 2019). According to Ahmed, various insurgency attempts inside Pakistan by the Indian forces compelled Pakistan to lower its diplomatic relations with India (Ahmed, 2015).

India's abrogation of Article 370 exacerbated political alienation among Kashmiri leaders leading to aggravated unrest. Bhat argues that 370's removal was constitutional and necessary to curb separation and promote economic investment (Bhat, 2019). On the contrary, Pakistani views it as a violation of human rights and condemned the move as illegal and a betrayal to the constitutional norms (Bhukhari, 2021). Amnesty International documented mass detention, restrictions on political activities, and communication blackouts post-revocation (Amnesty International, 2020).

Duschinski & Ghosh reveal that a surge in homegrown militancy, with youth joining freedom fighter groups (Duschinski & Ghosh, 2022), India accuses Pakistan for cross-border terrorism while Islamabad denies direct involvement and argues that India fuels the terrorism within the region (Shah et al., 2021). Singh argues that this revocation reflects the

agenda of PM Modi, emphasizing national integration over national autonomy (Singh, 2022). On contrary, Pakistan's effort to connect both the nations through Kartarpur Corridor as a gesture of good will but Indian prejudice creates unrest within the region (Ullah et al., 2022). Fraid & Sarwar reveal that the means of warfare have shifted from traditional to modern by adopting and introducing Artificial Intelligence to secure national security (Farid & Sarwar, 2024).

Like Kashmir, Israel-Palestine conflict remains one of the most complex geopolitical issue witnessing significant developments that have shaped its trajectory including US foreign policy in regional alliance and evolving international responses. The peace process and Abraham Accords initiated by the USA were hailed as a breakthrough and many believed that normalize the relations between Israel and several Arab states but on the contrary, critics argue that these agreements sidelined Palestinian interests, effectively abandoning the two-state solution (Kurtzer et al., 2021; Lynch, 2019). Lynch reveals that USA decision to recognize Jerusalem as Israel's capital in 2017 sparked a contentious debate, widespread Palestinian protests and international condemnation (Lynch, 2019). Erakat argues that these actions significantly undermined the prospect for a negotiated settlement (Erakat, 2019).

Israel's expansionist policies complicating the possibility of a future Palestinian state by increasing violence between settlers and Palestinian with human rights violations and systematic harassment and displacement. The critics believe that Israel has effectively created a one-state reality, albeit without granting equal rights to Palestinians (Gordon, 2024; Tilley, 2021). The ongoing conflict has made dire humanitarian situation in Gaza, devastated Gaza's infrastructure and deepened the humanitarian catastrophe. Feldman argues that violence in Gaza as a managed conflict in which neither side has an incentive to pursue a lasting resolution (Feldman, 2020). Kahlidi describes it the lack of democratic accountability on both sides has contributed to a sense of hopelessness (Khalidi, 2021). According to Sayigh, regional actors including Egypt, Turkey, and Qatar have played significant roles in mediating ceasefires and providing humanitarian aid to Gaza (Sayigh, 2020). In South Asia, the China's rise as a potential

mediator has also sparked speculation about its future role in the conflict (Scobell, 2023).

The Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflict has been characterized by escalating tensions and growing humanitarian crisis. Therefore, regional actor's especially Muslim countries including Pakistan are trying to provide peaceful solution. In the case of Kashmir, China and Turkey significantly support Pakistan stance and offers diplomatic as well strategic assistance. Pakistan also backed Palestinian struggle and diplomatically oppose Israel's stance and emphasizes on a two-nation policy within the territory of Palestine. In modern diplomacy, propaganda has become a central instrument to construct narratives, public opinion, and influence both domestic and international perceptions. In Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflicts states use propaganda as part of diplomatic strategy. Therefore, Pakistan for diplomatic response uses such narratives to cultivate international support and reinforce its identity as a defender of Muslim causes. In international relations, propaganda defines as the systematic dissemination of information misleading or deliberately manipulative by states, non-states actors to shape public opinion, influence foreign policy and advance geopolitical objectives. Jowett & O'Donnell refer propaganda as strategically designed to evoke emotional responses and reinforce ideological narratives. Taylor explains it disinformation campaigns in the 21st century for personal gains (Taylor, 2013; Jowett & O'Donnell, 2018). Muneer and Zeib discuss that Pakistan employs framing to emphasize occupation and human rights violation, contrasting Indian-Israeli narratives those frame these issues as internal security matters. According to Entman, framing theory is defined as strategic highlighting of certain facets of reality to construct an interpretation. Therefore, Pakistan's discursive strategy as rooted in identities and normative stances because it constructs itself as a postcolonial Muslim state defending oppressed Kashmiris and Palestinians. Pakistan's echoing anticolonial narratives and challenging western hegemony in narrative diplomacy.

Theoretical Framework

This theoretical framework discusses Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflict through three different theories including constructivism, framing, and postcolonial theory that provides how identities and social

perceptions shape propaganda narratives and diplomatic response.

Constructivism Theory

Constructivism focuses on the role of ideas, norms, identity, and social interactions in shaping the behavior of states and international actors. As Wendt contends that “anarchy is what states make of it” meaning that everything is socially constructed not determined by natural laws (Wendt, 1992). The core themes of constructivism are:

- Ideas and beliefs matter
- Social interaction constructs reality
- Norms and identity shape interests
- Change is possible

Pakistan’s alignment with Kashmir and Palestine conflicts is a reflection of its self-ascribed role and constructs its identity as a Muslim-majority state advocating for oppressed Muslim populations and how this shapes its foreign policy. However, Kashmir issue is not just a territorial dispute; it is deeply embedded in the constructed identities of both India-Pakistan and shapes diplomatic responses. Pakistan’s political rhetoric frames Kashmir as the unfinished agenda of 1947 partition. This narrative echoed in political speeches, taught in textbooks, and reinforced through national commemorations. Indian political discourses perceive Kashmir as an integral part of India. Like Kashmir, in Israel-Palestine conflict, constructivism is equally effective in analyzing the conflict where identity politics and competing historical narratives are at the core of the dispute.

Framing Theory

According to Goffman and Entman, framing theory examines how states construct and promote specific narratives to shape public and international perception (Goffman, 1974; Entman, 1993). There are four core elements of framing theory.

- Problem Definition: highlight the issue
- Causal Interpretation: identifies who causes the problem
- Moral Evaluation: make judgment about the issue
- Treatment: Suggest solutions or response

In simple words, Framing is not about ‘what’ is reported but ‘how’ it reported an issue. In Kashmir-

Palestine conflicts, India and Pakistan both use distinct framing strategies to shape global and domestic narratives. India frames Kashmir conflict through the lens of national security and counterterrorism. On contrary, Pakistan frames Kashmir as a human rights colonial occupation emphasizes the plight of Kashmiris and the illegitimacy of India’s unilateral decisions. Indian media outlets frame revocation of 370 as a step toward development and peace but Pakistan counters it as a violation of international law and forceful subjugation (Ali, 2017). The Israel-Palestine conflict is highly susceptible to competing frames, shaped by media bias, political ideology, and global power alignments. Israel frames its actions as self-defense, and the right to defend its citizens. On contrary, pro Palestinian outlets frame this situation as one of occupation, apartheid, and ethnic cleansing. The international media struggle with balanced view frames terms like ‘clashes’ or ‘conflict’ instead of ‘occupation’ or ‘siege’ and undermine actual issue (Said, 2007). Both Kashmir and Palestine, comparatively framed differently because ethno- religious identity claims and intense state control of information. Yet Palestine receives significant international attention due to the involvement of the USA and West. On the other side, Kashmir is framed as a bilateral issue between India and Pakistan. In the nutshell, framing theory explains how narratives influence not just public opinion but international policy and humanitarian responses. Both Kashmir and Palestine conflicts frame their struggle in terms of rights, freedom, and justice. Pakistan’s diplomatic response influenced by these narratives and shaped by public opinion due to religious sentiments. Therefore, Pakistan frames both conflicts and cases of illegal occupation while deliberately avoiding the securitized frames used by India and Israel.

Postcolonial Theory

Postcolonial theory discusses the legacy of colonialism and power structures in international narratives useful to critique dominated Western media discourses and international silence regarding Kashmir and Palestine. Postcolonial theory explains how Western narratives marginalize non-Western voices (Saud, 1988). Relevantly, Pakistan’s diplomatic stance reflects a postcolonial critique of imperialism, drawing parallels between Indian illegal occupation of Kashmir and

Palestine by India and Israel respectively. This theory challenges the dominant geopolitical discourses and exposes the double standards in international human rights enforcement. It is a critical framework that examines the legacy and ongoing impacts of colonialism on contemporary societies and challenges Eurocentric knowledge, voices and experiences (Spivak, 1999). Postcolonial theory core ideas are:

- Colonial Legacy
- Othering and representation
- Hybridity and identity
- Resistance and Subaltern Voices

India-Pakistan's conflict over Kashmir can be interpreted as a postcolonial crisis in the unfinished legacies of British imperialism that left Kashmir's fate unsettled due to Britain's hasty exit and ambiguous decisions (Snedden, 2015). India's illegal control often defended as a project of national integration. India's use of violence in Kashmir reflects colonial modes of control and this theory helps frame this not just a security issue, but as a re-inscription of colonial power over Muslim majority regions (Zia, 2019). The examination of Palestine conflict through the lens of postcolonial theory reveals that Zionist project in Palestine represents a form of settler colonialism where an external; population claims indigenous land and seeks to erase the native population (Khalidi, 2020). This theory provides thoughtful insights to understand both Kashmir and Palestine as sites of ongoing colonial and neocolonial domination.

Philosophical Framework

This section discusses the philosophical framework to analyze the Kashmir-Israel-Palestine conflict.

Constructivist Epistemology/ Interpretivism

As discussed above in constructivism theory, Interpretivism assumes that reality is socially constructed through language, discourse, and interaction. Constructivist epistemology justifies the use of qualitative methodologies that seek to understand meaning and power in propaganda narratives and diplomatic texts. Interpretivism critically challenges dominant knowledge systems and advocates for the marginalized (Berger & Luckmann, 2016). This study focuses Pakistan's role as a voice for the Kashmiri and Palestinian people on counter-

hegemonic narratives. According to Scott, Interpretivist argues that the world is not merely observed, it is interpreted (Scott, 2017). The core ideas of this philosophy are:

- Reality is socially constructed and identity matters

The application of interpretivism on Kashmir issue reveals that competing narratives between India and Pakistan construct perceptions and influence diplomatic affiliations. On Palestine conflict, it helps unpack how identities, memory, and international norms drive political narratives. This theory argues that Pakistan's diplomatic behavior is best understood through identity-based motivations and norm entrepreneurship because Pakistan positions itself as a guardian of Muslim causes and constantly supports Palestine and Kashmir's right to self-determination. This epistemology contends that state actions are influenced by how states perceive themselves and their roles in global society.

Islamic Ethical Framework

Islamic ethical framework explains Islamic political thought emphasizes Justice, solidarity, and opposition to oppression, closely aligns with interpretivist epistemology. Islamic ethical framework is significant when examining Muslim-majority responses to global injustice especially Pakistan's position on Kashmir and Palestine (Ramadan, 2009). These two conflicts have been framed as ethical imperatives in the Islamic consciousness of the state and its people. Through this lens, Pakistan emphasizes on justice and solidarity with oppressed Muslim communities. Pakistani frame Kashmir issue as a moral and religious duty to stand by a fellow Muslim population. Therefore, Pakistan's diplomatic narratives emphasize human rights violations and support Kashmir as part of an Islamic ethical commitment. In Palestinian case, Pakistan has same religious commitments. These Islamic ethics provide a normative justification for Pakistan's diplomatic behavior.

Kashmir-Israel-Palestine Analogy: Pakistan's Positioning

The unresolved Kashmir-Palestine conflicts serve for Pakistan as emblematic cases through which state articulates its ideological commitments, foreign policy

priorities, and international positioning. This research study seeks to examine how propaganda narratives shape perceptions and influence diplomatic response. Propaganda is a deliberate, systematic attempt to shape perceptions, manipulate cognitions and direct behavior to achieve a response that furthers the desired intent of the propagandist. In modern days, media as propaganda tool uses to interpret desired perception and construct public opinion. Pakistani media outlets amplified voice for Kashmiri identity, countering Indian narratives of normalization in occupied Kashmir. Saud & Kazim explain that Pakistan faces Indian disinformation campaigns branding it as chaotic to shape false-flag narratives in Kashmir (Saud & Kazim, 2022). This digital propaganda and information warfare polarizes public perceptions and constructs false narratives. Pakistani and Indian political actors polarize social media and shape domestic and Diaspora discourse. On the other side, Pakistani leaders consistently condemned Israeli actions, framing them as war crimes and violations of international law. Pakistan's Islamic affiliations call for Palestinian freedom, including strong appeals for Al-Aqsa protection and humanitarian action. Shah describes how Pakistan systematically draws parallels between Kashmir and Palestine to amplify its moral narratives (Shah & Tilwani, 2024). Pakistani leaders compared Indian action in Kashmir to Israeli apartheid and Nazi ideology as raised by Pakistani Prime Minister Imran Khan in the United Nations General Assembly. However, the political landscape has shifted from affiliations to interests.

Pakistan's Diplomatic response and Propaganda Narratives

Pakistan has a principled stance that both Kashmir and Palestine represent unresolved issues of illegal occupation and denial of fundamental rights. Pakistan has consistently raised the issue at the United Nations, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), and other international platforms, reiterating its support for a UN-mandated plebiscite as outlined in the UN Security Council Resolutions (UNSC Resolutions 47, 1948). Pakistan has crafted a sustained diplomatic narrative, supported by strategic use of media, multilateral diplomacy, and rhetorical devices that emphasize resistance, justice, and Islamic solidarity. Pakistan's response is also entangled with propaganda

narratives—both as a tool of influence and as a countermeasure against the narratives emerging from adversaries like India and Israel.

Pakistan's diplomatic rhetoric has been enhanced by the use of emotionally charged imagery, references to human rights violations, and comparisons to colonialism and apartheid, especially drawing analogies between Kashmir and Palestine. Pakistani leaders, including Prime Ministers Imran Khan and Shehbaz Sharif, have frequently drawn parallels between Indian actions in Kashmir and Israeli practices in the occupied Palestinian territories. This comparative framing aligns with broader Islamic world sentiment and bolsters Pakistan's position as a defender of Muslim causes. This diplomatic response to the Israel-Palestine conflict is equally resolute. It has refused to recognize Israel as a legitimate state, arguing that doing so would betray the Palestinian people and their struggle for statehood with East Jerusalem as their capital. At the UN General Assembly, Human Rights Council, and OIC, Pakistan has condemned Israeli settlements, military aggression in Gaza, and the expansionist policies of the Netanyahu government. This stance remains unchanged even after the Abraham Accords, wherein several Arab countries normalized relations with Israel. At international level, Pakistan's diplomatic missions disseminate curated information packages, host seminars, and engage with think tanks to frame these conflicts within human rights, international law, and self-determination discourse (Aljazeera, 2019). These diplomatic efforts are supported by strategic partnerships with international media outlets, NGOs, and civil society organizations sympathetic to the Kashmiri and Palestinian causes. Pakistan also collaborates with diasporic communities in the UK, US, and Middle East to maintain visibility of the issues in Western capitals. The goal is not only to counter Indian and Israeli narratives but also to mobilize broader global support from human rights groups and pro-justice movements. Pakistan's diplomatic efficacy has often been limited by shifting global geopolitics, including India's growing economic and strategic clout and Israel's deep ties with Western powers and Gulf monarchies. Nevertheless, Pakistan continues to emphasize the moral and legal dimensions of these conflicts, portraying itself as a consistent advocate of international law. It uses this moral capital to resist

normalization with Israel and to counterbalance India's regional influence.

Ahmed argues that Pakistan's diplomatic messaging on Kashmir and Palestine demonstrates a consistent use of moral framing, rooted in religious and humanitarian principles (Ahmed, 2022). According to Hussain, the increasing digital sophistication of Pakistani propaganda tools—particularly social media diplomacy and strategic visual narratives—has somewhat improved its global advocacy, especially among civil society actors (Hussain, 2021).

However, critics like Rizvi (2023) warn that unless Pakistan complements narrative building with hard diplomacy and alliance formation, especially in the post-Abraham Accord environment, its messaging may remain more symbolic than impactful.

In conclusion, Pakistan's diplomatic response to the Kashmir and Palestine conflicts is shaped by ideological commitment, domestic political imperatives, and the need to counter regional adversaries through moral and legal advocacy. Propaganda narratives, carefully curated and deployed, remain central to this diplomatic engagement, functioning as both instruments of national cohesion and tools for international persuasion. These narratives, rooted in the language of human rights, resistance, and Islamic solidarity, allow Pakistan to project its foreign policy positions while challenging the legitimacy of opposing state actions in Kashmir and Palestine.

Pakistan's Foreign Policy towards Israel

Pakistan has no foreign relation with Israel. Since independence, Pakistan's foreign policy has been shifting due to socio-religious pressure. The inconsistent foreign policy behavior compels Pakistan to do bids for the major power of the world. Therefore, with shifting dynamics of the world politics, this paper argues that Pakistan has to formulate a new perspective towards Israel. Despite enormous opposition and criticism, many states like Turkey, Sudan, and UAE recognized Israel and have friendly relations based on national interests. The UAE-Israel agreement is more significant for the Arab world than Israel. For future outcomes, Pakistan's foreign policy towards Israel can be discerned and further built upon and this paper argues that Pakistan can do much more for the Palestinians if it can do what need to be done for

Pakistanis (Ali et al., 2016; Fox, 2019). Despite backchannel diplomacy, UAE and Saudi Arabia ties with Israel, suggest that Pakistan have to reframe its policy in near future and most notable, Indo- Israel bonhomie threatens the national interests of Pakistan.

India-Israel Defense Ties: Security Threat for Pakistan

The defense ties between India-Israel focuses on the military relationship are likely to create serious security challenges for Pakistan. Both nations seek to gain power and dream of territorial hegemon concerns Pakistan's balance of power in the region (Farid & Adnan, 2022). India-Israel defense ties have emerged as a significant axis in South Asian geopolitics and encompass intelligence sharing, joint defense production, and anti-terrorism cooperation. These agreements pose direct threat and serious national security concerns for Pakistan. Israel provides drones, missiles, and surveillance equipment to India that strengthens its ground capabilities. To counter India and balancing power in the South Asian region, Pakistan must think out of the box and propose a workable policy towards Israel to secure national integrity. Pakistan, like UAE, Bahrain, and other Arab nations can initiate foreign relations with Israel. In policy, Pakistan must frame two state solution of Palestine as top priority. Pakistan's friendly ties with Israel not only enhance its international standings but it can be beneficial for trade, agriculture, and economic agreements and for Palestine as it would be able to sit with Israel on negotiating table. It is advisable to adapt to the changing geopolitical landscape and to counter India politically and economically.

Redefining Diplomacy of Pakistan: Discussion and Analysis

Foreign policy plays an important role in uplifting a nation and constitutes diplomatic ties including political, economic, and strategic. Despite Pakistan's rigorous efforts to support the cause of Kashmir and Palestine, it has become imperative to frame new standards of international relations to encompass the broader dimensions of global political dynamics. In this regard, Pakistani leaders and politicians need to stop politicize Kashmir and Palestine issue to mitigate the polarization from the population. Polarization has

transformed the global political landscape and divisive rhetoric (Sarwar & Aziz, 2024). However, it is evident that India and Israel both equally violating and mass murdering the innocent Muslim people, therefore, the top provision of the new foreign policy emphasizes on a peaceful and impartial resolution of both the conflicts according to the native population. All Muslim nations and economic giants including China need to curb Israel and India from killing the innocent via United Nations resolutions and negotiations.

There are two main reasons why Pakistan needs to refocus its stance from 'no relation to have relation' with Israel. First, Indo-Israel defense ties are a direct threat to Pakistan's national security. To mitigate Indian influence in the region and maintain balance of power in the region, it has become significant that Pakistan must develop a pragmatic foreign policy towards Israel like UAE and Bahrain did. This shift in Pakistan's foreign policy can play as a counter strike to India. Second, Pakistan can do more for Kashmiri and Palestinian when it is able to make equal decisions and share mutual interests. With the help of Arab-Israel friendly nations, Pakistan can propose solutions to the existing problem. This act connects regional actors through connectivity projects that resulted in economic growth and effective governing frameworks (Rashid & Sarwar, 2025).

New Policy Shift: Challenges

Socio-religious values are deep rooted in Pakistan's ideology that influence decision making and shape diplomatic narratives. The religious groups are active and influence public opinion and constructs perceptions. These socio-religious segments of the society do not allow policy makers to navigate independently. Political instability and economic woes of Pakistan are major hurdles in policy making. Pakistan must address these issues at urgent basis and shift from traditional thinking to modern means of political influencers. It offers opportunities that will open the door for regional cooperation and peace.

Conclusion

Pakistan has historical stance against India and Israel's illegal occupation of Kashmir and Palestine respectively. Solely, Pakistan sustains its position as a vocal advocate for Kashmiri and Palestinian rights. Pakistan's diplomatic approach to the Kashmir and

Palestine issues underscores the importance of narrative construction in foreign policy, where moral authority, symbolic alignment, and consistent advocacy serve not only as tools of resistance but also as means of shaping international discourse. The challenge ahead lies in converting these narratives into tangible diplomatic gains amid an increasingly polarized and transactional global order. This paper suggests that Pakistan can be more assertive when it shifts its policy towards Israel and has the ability to become a game changer and peacemaker in the world. However, various challenges including socio-religious, economic, and political, Pakistan needs to construct a new foreign policy to mitigate these challenges. India's defense relation with Israel poses a direct threat to Pakistan's national security. By adopting modern techniques, Pakistan shapes new diplomatic response to counter India's dream of regional hegemon and maintain the balance of power. Pakistan's positive response to international actors can enhance its influence worldwide. The effectiveness of Pakistan's diplomatic rhetoric is often constrained by shifting alliance and the realpolitik of international powers. Yet, Pakistan continues to align itself with legal norms, partnering with human rights.

References

- Ahmad, B. N. (2015). Future of War and Strategy: Indo-Pak Dynamics. Islamabad Policy Research Institute Journal, 15(1), 1-20.
- Ahmed, A. (2022). Pakistan's Diplomatic Narratives: Framing Kashmir and Palestine in International Law. Routledge.
- Al Jazeera. (2019). "Imran Khan: Kashmir and Palestine Are Connected Struggles."
- Ali, A. (2017). Kashmir conflict and South Asian elite press: A framing analysis. Journal of Politics and International Studies, 3(02), 47-62.
- Ali, M., Banks, G., & Parsons, N. (2016). US-Israel Special Aid Relationship Dynamics and Implications for Pakistan. Policy Perspectives: The Journal of the Institute of Policy Studies, 13(2), 109129. https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1316/9/polipers.13.2.0109#metadata_info_tab_contents

- Berger, P., & Luckmann, T. (2016). The social construction of reality. In *Social theory re-wired* (pp. 110-122). Routledge.
- Bhat, B. A. (2019). A study on Jammu and Kashmir present, past and views of students on Article 370 Abrogation. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 2(12), 3-7.
- Bukhari, M., Muzammal, T., & Latif, M. I. (2021). Modi and Kashmir: Future Prospects. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 74-82.
- Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of communication*, 43(4), 51-58.
- Erakat, N. (2020). Justice for some: Law and the question of Palestine. Stanford University Press.
- Farid, A., & Adnan, M. (2022). India-Israel Defense Ties: Security Threat for Pakistan. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 76-87.
- Farid, A., & Sarwar, G. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and National Security: Future Warfare Implications for Pakistan. *Annals of Human and Social Sciences*, 5(2), 446-459.
- Feldman, N. (2020). The Arab winter: A tragedy.
- Fox, E. (2019). Colonialism in Israel/Palestine: Bedouin Indigeneity & Racialized Religious Definitions.
- Ghosh, S. N., & Duschinski, H. (2022). The Writ of Liberty in the Courts of Kashmir. In *Routledge Handbook of Critical Kashmir Studies* (pp. 115-126). Routledge.
- Goffman, E. (1974). *Frame analysis: An essay on the organization of experience*. Harvard University Press.
- Gordon, N. (2024). Between Human Rights and Civil Society: The Case of Israel's Apartheid Enablers. *Law & Social Inquiry*, 49(3), 1426-1452.
- Hussain, S. S., Mustafa, G., Imran, M., & Nawaz, A. (2019). The Indo-Pak Rivalry and the Kashmir Issue: A Historical Analysis in the Security Context of South Asia. *J. Pol. Stud.*, 26, 73.
- Hussain, Z. (2021). "Propaganda, Diplomacy and the Digital Battlefield." *Journal of Strategic Affairs*, 6(2), 45-61.
- Jowett, G. S., & O'donnell, V. (2018). *Propaganda & persuasion*. Sage publications.
- Khalidi, R. (2020). *The hundred years' war on Palestine: A history of settler colonialism and resistance, 1917-2017*. Metropolitan Books.
- Khalidi, R. (2020). *The hundred years' war on Palestine: A history of settler colonialism and resistance, 1917-2017*. Metropolitan Books.
- Lynch, M. (2016). *The new Arab wars: Uprisings and anarchy in the Middle East*. Public Affairs.
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Pakistan. (2023). "Pakistan's Official Position on the Palestine and Kashmir Issues."
- Ramadan, T. (2009). *Radical reform: Islamic ethics and liberation*. Oxford University Press.
- Rashid, M. I., & Sarwar, G. (2025). *Infrastructure Diplomacy and Economic Growth: Impacts of Regional Connectivity Projects on Pakistan*. *Pakistan Languages and Humanities Review*, 9(2), 218-232.
- Rizvi, H. (2023). "Limits of Moral Diplomacy: Pakistan's Advocacy for Kashmir and Palestine." *South Asian Foreign Policy Review*, 9(1), 80-98.
- Said, E. W. (1977). Orientalism. *The Georgia Review*, 31(1), 162-206.
- Said, E. W. (2007). *The end of the peace process: Oslo and after*. Vintage.
- Sarwar, G., & Aziz, A. (2024). Populism and Political Polarization: Cross-National Comparison of Populist Politics. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*, 2(04), 155-168.
- Saud, A., & Kazim, N. (2022). Disinformation and Propaganda Tactics: Impacts of Indian Information Warfare on Pakistan. *Journal of Indian Studies*, 8(02), 335-354.
- Sayigh, Y. (1997). *Armed struggle and the search for state: The Palestinian national movement, 1949-1993*. Oxford University Press.
- Scobell, A., & Nader, A. (2016). *China in the Middle East: The wary dragon*. RAND corporation.
- Scott, D. (2017). Interpretivism as a Theory of Knowledge. *The BERA/SAGE Handbook of Educational Research: Two Volume Set*, 2, 243-258.

- Shah, A. H., & Tilwani, S. A. (2024). Representation of Palestine and Kashmir Conflict in English Literature: A Study of Selected Works. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 15(6), 2051-2059.
- Shah, Z., Shah, S., Shah, J., & Khan, A. (2023). Indian Revocation of Kashmir's Special Status: Causes and Implications. *Bulletin of Business and Economics (BBE)*, 12(4), 755-761.
- Shamim, S. J., Nasim, M. M., & Ali, T. (2024). Indo-Pak conflict in South Asia: dynamics of Kashmir issue and the way forward for peace. *Asian Journal of Politicology and Allied Studies (AJPAS)*, 2(1), 1-10.
- Singh, P. (2020). The Modi government and the revocation of Article 370: A critical analysis. *Journal of Indian Politics*, 11(2), 50-65.
- Snedden, C. (2015). *Understanding kashmir and kashmiris*. Oxford University Press.
- Spivak, G. C. (1999). *A critique of postcolonial reason: Toward a history of the vanishing present*. Harvard university press.
- Taylor, P. M. (2013). *Munitions of the mind: A history of propaganda from the ancient world to the present era*. In *Munitions of the Mind*. Manchester University Press.
- Tilley, V. (2005). *The one-state solution: A breakthrough for peace in the Israeli-Palestinian deadlock*. Manchester University Press.
- Ullah, M. S., Sarwar, G., & Daraz, U. (2022). Kartarpur Corridor: Re-defining Security in South Asian Region. *Annals of Human and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 01-09.
- Wendt, A. (1992). Anarchy is what states make of it: the social construction of power politics. *International organization*, 46(2), 391-425.
- Zia, A. (2019). *Resisting disappearance: Military occupation and women's activism in Kashmir*. In *Resisting Disappearance*. University of Washington Press.